

THE EXPANSION OF CHILEAN CHERRY EXPORTS AND THE CHALLENGES OF THE CHINESE MARKET

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Abstract

In recent years, Chile has experienced significant growth in cherry production. The sustained expansion of cultivated area, export volumes, and export values reflects this trend. China has consolidated its position as the primary destination for Chilean cherries, consistently accounting for more than 90% of total exports each season. This high level of concentration is largely explained by the premium prices paid by Chinese consumers, particularly during the Chinese New Year, given the fruit's strong cultural significance. Chilean producers remain optimistic, expecting prices to remain high and production to continue expanding in the short term. In some industry discussions, it has been suggested that Chile would struggle to meet Chinese demand even if the planted area of cherry orchards were to double. At the same time, stakeholders have raised concerns about the risks associated with reliance on a single export market, including potential exposure to retaliatory measures in the event of diplomatic tensions. Current challenges appear to stem less from demand constraints and more from supply-side limitations, as signs are emerging that agro-industrial development in Chile may be reaching its limits, mainly due to water scarcity and labor shortages.

1. Contextual Background

In Latin America, agricultural production is increasingly oriented toward integration into international value chains. Argentina and Brazil are recognized as major agri-food producers due to their large-scale production of soybeans and other staple crops essential to the global diet. In contrast, Chile and Colombia have focused on niche markets that demand high-quality agricultural products with specific characteristics.

This study examines the case of Chile, where fruit exports have facilitated the country's integration into highly competitive global food markets. Cherries have become one of Chile's most dynamic export products in recent decades. In 2021, cherries became the country's leading export outside the copper sector (La Tercera, 2021a). During the 2020/2021 season, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, Chile exported 353,000 tons of cherries valued at approximately USD 1,853 million FOB, making cherries the top fruit export by value and the third by volume (La Tercera, 2021b).

China is the primary destination for Chilean cherry exports, accounting for 91% of shipments in the 2023 season. Although export growth has been closely

associated with the expansion of the Chinese market, the development of Chile's cherry industry and the growth of Chinese demand are distinct processes. Nonetheless, sustained demand from China has strongly encouraged production expansion.

The Lunar New Year represents a peak period for cherry sales, as Chile's harvest season coincides with the holiday. Cherries are highly valued in China for their taste and visual appeal, particularly their red color, sweetness, and juiciness. Red is culturally associated with luck and prosperity, and round fruits are traditionally exchanged as gifts during the celebration, symbolizing wishes for happiness, prosperity, and good health. In this context, the Chinese ambassador to Chile described cherries as "the perfect gift," highlighting their dark red color and sweet flavor as symbols of good fortune and prosperity (Simfruit, 2023). Chilean companies actively promote available varieties on social media, emphasizing their relevance to the Lunar New Year market, and producers commonly pack the cherries in bright red boxes. Their relatively high price and perceived sophistication further reinforce their status as a premium product.

Chile's cherry export sector has demonstrated resilience in the face of international challenges, consolidating its position as the world's leading supplier. Despite logistical and economic difficulties, export volumes have continued to grow, reaching a record level in the 2022/2023 season (Tapia, 2023).

However, the high concentration of exports in a single market raises questions about long-term sustainability. Incidents such as the destruction of cherry shipments in January 2021, reportedly due to concerns over COVID-19 contamination, fueled speculation about possible political retaliation. These claims were later dismissed by Chinese authorities (La Tercera, 2021c).

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This case study assesses the implications of Chile's cherry export boom from a perspective that goes beyond conventional economic analysis. It considers structural constraints affecting agro-industrial development, including water management and labor availability, and examines the sector's capacity to manage pressures associated with continued expansion. The future of Chilean cherry exports may ultimately depend more on domestic production limits than on changes in China's trade or political behavior.

2. Methodology

This study employs a qualitative methodology. Data were collected through a review of interdisciplinary literature, analysis of specialized documents, and semi-structured interviews. The document review included government and private sources related to agri-food and fruit exports, as well as water and labor legislation. Interview participants were selected based on accessibility, relevance, expertise, and representativeness. They were grouped into two categories: academic experts and individuals directly involved in cherry production. All interviews were conducted under confidentiality protocols and addressed three main areas: cherry and fruit production in general, perspectives on agro-industrial development, and issues related to water management and labor shortages.

3. The Rise and Expansion of Chile’s Cherry Market Driven by Chinese Demand

In 2023, the fruit sector accounted for 9.4% of the country’s total export value in FOB dollars, according to data from Chilean Customs. Within this sector, cherries have emerged as a highly profitable product in a market traditionally dominated by apple and grape exports. In recent years, Chile has experienced what Serrano, Pérez, and De Abreu (2021) describe as a “cherry boom,” characterized by sustained growth in production, export volumes, and export revenues. Figure 1 shows the upward trend in the surface area

planted with cherry orchards between 2004 and 2022, based on 2023 data from ODEPA.

The expansion of cherry cultivation has been largely driven by export market profitability, as reflected in the increase in both export volumes and the value per exported ton (Figure 2). The export market is highly concentrated, as shown in Table 1, which lists the main destinations over the past five seasons. China clearly dominates as the primary recipient of Chilean cherry exports. Cherries are highly valued in China for their flavor and visual appeal—particularly their red color, sweetness, and juiciness. These attributes are culturally associated with positive wishes, and gifting cherries conveys friendship and gratitude, especially during the Chinese New Year.

Figure 1:
Evolution of the surface area used for cherry cultivation in Chile.

Source: Authors, based on ODEPA (2023).

Figure 2:

Annual volume of cherries exported by Chile, in tons

Source: Authors, based on FaoStat (2023).

Table 1:

Main export destinations of Chilean cherries over the last five seasons (in tons)

Destination/season	2018 - 2019	2019 - 2020	2020 - 2021	2021 - 2022	2022 - 2023
China/Hong Kong	158.434	207.775	322.188	313.943	365.201
USA	4.773	4.442	6.572	12.471	17.819
South Korea	4.169	3.224	5.533	6.900	6.546
Taiwan	2.235	1.954	4.596	5.998	6.426
Brazil	2.329	2.784	2.129	2.659	3.895

Note: From the 2019-2020 Yearbook. IQConsulting, 2020.

Table 2 presents data on export volumes and the average price per kilogram of cherries in China over the past four seasons. These per-kilogram figures represent seasonal averages, as prices fluctuate significantly throughout the marketing cycle, which revolves around the Chinese New Year. Although retail prices in China are high, revenues are distributed across the production chain. As of December 2023,

producer returns have ranged between USD 4 and USD 8 per kilogram, depending on quality, timing of sale, and shipping method. Compared with other fruit crops, cherry production offers relatively high returns.

Although cherries were cultivated in Chile well before the expansion of Chinese demand, the recent surge has reinforced the country's position as one of the

Table 2
Arrived volume and weighted average price per kilogram of cherries in China over the last five seasons

Season	Volume arriving in China (tons)	Weighted Average Price (USD/KG)
2017 -2018	161.011	17,42
2018 - 2019	158.434	13,25
2019 - 2020	207.755	11,99
2020 - 2021	322.188	10,39
2021 - 2022	313.943	9,9

Note: Authors, based on FAOStat and ODEPA (2023).

world's leading producers and exporters. Growing demand in China has been supported by more diversified consumption patterns and the seasonal scarcity of cherries in the Northern Hemisphere during the Chinese New Year (ASOEX, 2023).

To support market expansion, the Chilean Fruit Exporters Association (ASOEX) created the Cherry Committee, which includes approximately 90 companies and seeks to broaden demand beyond China's largest cities (ProChile, 2019). Promotional campaigns are conducted through platforms such as fruitsfromchile.com under the slogan "Cherish Every Moment." Marketing initiatives in China have included events such as "Super Cherries Day" and influencer-driven social media campaigns (ProChile, 2019). During "Chile Week China" in Chengdu in October 2023,

President Gabriel Boric emphasized the diversification of Chilean exports beyond copper and cherries (CNN Chile, 2023).

In recent years, Chinese market requirements have become more demanding, particularly regarding fruit size, color, and phytosanitary standards. Cherries larger than 28 mm in diameter are currently preferred, whereas five years ago 26 mm fruit was widely accepted. A significant price gap has emerged, and smaller calibers have lost market value; fruit under 12 mm is no longer packed.¹ This shift has encouraged

¹ As of December 2023, cherries are classified into the size categories L, XL, J, 2J, 3J, 4J, and 5J. The most demanded calibers are 2J and 3J (26–28 mm in diameter), typically exhibiting dark coloration (D or D+).

producers to prioritize larger cherries with darker coloration, as these characteristics command higher prices in the Chinese market.

Quality—including compliance with phytosanitary standards—has become increasingly critical. In 2023, rainfall caused fruit cracking, reducing acceptance in the Chinese market. The ASOEX Cherry Committee has emphasized quality control but has faced challenges related to the poor condition of early shipments. These issues altered domestic perceptions of the Chinese market, which had previously been viewed as less demanding, and highlighted the need to maintain high standards to remain competitive. The

growing selectivity of Chinese consumers has become more evident, leading to greater attention to quality throughout the production and export process.

There is a widespread perception in Chile that cherry production and exports can continue to expand, supported by expectations of sustained Chinese demand. While doubts remain regarding Chile's capacity to fully satisfy that demand, the Chinese market is generally expected to remain stable, with no major disruptions anticipated (Tapia, 2023). Nevertheless, concerns persist about the feasibility of continued expansion given the structural constraints of Chile's agro-industrial development model (ProChile, 2019).

Photo 1:

Box of Chilean cherries exported to China (photograph by Magdalena Gil)

4. Impact and Strategies of Chinese Influence on Commodity Trade in Latin America

How does the case of Chilean cherries fit within broader Latin American trends in agricultural exports? This section situates the case within the wider context of China's growing demand for raw materials and its impact on the region. It examines debates surrounding economic dependence and reprimarization, and analyzes China's role in shaping bilateral trade patterns, including the implications of its low-cost production strategy.

4.1. China's Food Security

Carol Wise and Victoria Chonn Ching (2018) note that China played a crucial role in the commodity boom at the beginning of the 21st century. Between 2003 and 2013, commodity prices doubled or even tripled, largely driven by China's demand for energy, natural resources, and food. During this period, Latin American countries deepened trade ties with China—relationships that persisted even after commodity prices declined and China's economic growth slowed in 2013 (Vadell, 2019). Latin America became a key supplier of primary goods to China, while manufactured products flowed in the opposite direction.²

China's growing presence in Latin American economies has generated debate regarding economic dependence and the reprimarization of the region. Authors such as Jenkins (2012) and Wise and Chonn Ching (2018) attribute rising trade flows primarily to domestic

resource constraints within China and caution against overstating its regional impact. In contrast, Barton and Rehner (2018) and Costa, Garred, and Pessoa (2014) argue that China's low-cost production strategy has reshaped trade dynamics and produced disruptive effects in local economies. Ferchen (2011) links the surge in raw material demand to China's heavy-industry strategy, suggesting that the commodity boom was largely driven by internal structural factors within China and may therefore be subject to future domestic shifts.

It is undeniable that China has become a major trading partner for several Latin American countries, with agricultural trade playing a central role. Today, China faces the challenge of ensuring food security for a population of more than 1.4 billion people (Zhan, 2017). Freeman, Holslag, and Weil (2008) emphasize that food security is closely tied to political stability and government legitimacy in China. Socioeconomic development has been used to offset limited political openness, and authorities seek to prevent social unrest that could arise from food shortages or rising prices. As dietary patterns diversify, China has increasingly sought access to a broader range of imported food products.

Gooch and Gale (2018) argue that China's food security strategy has become increasingly linked to the globalization of its agricultural sector, marking a shift away from strict self-sufficiency. They note that China's 11th Five-Year Plan (2006–2010) encouraged firms to cultivate grains, seeds, and sugar on leased land abroad and import the output back to China. They also highlight that this trend toward agricultural "globalization" intensified with Xi Jinping's rise to power, particularly through the 2012 food security strategy and the Belt and Road Initiative launched in 2013. In practice, this led to investments in neighboring regions, specifically Southeast Asia and Russia, due to their geographic proximity and abundant land resources (Gooch & Gale, 2018).

² For a broader discussion of Chile–China relations in recent years, see, among others, Gachúz Maya and Urdinez (2022); Muñoz, López, and Bórquez (2022); Montt Strabucchi (2023); and Wise (2023).

Despite its central role in global commodity trade, China's direct agricultural investments in Latin America have been more limited than other forms of engagement. The 2004 "soybean crisis" provides insight into China's agribusiness strategy in the region. The literature indicates that China has relied largely on indirect strategies to secure access to commodities, including participation in different stages of the production chain, infrastructure development, diplomatic engagement, and financial cooperation.

In 2000, China surpassed the European Union as the world's largest soybean importer. To reduce dependence on U.S.-based intermediaries—particularly the firms known as the ABCD group (ADM, Bunge, Cargill, and Louis Dreyfus)—China sought closer commercial ties with Brazil (Giraudó, 2019). However, trade relations were disrupted in 2004 by two key developments that gave way to what became known as the "soybean crisis". Brazil authorized the cultivation of genetically modified soybeans in certain states, leading to the widespread adoption of transgenic seeds. In some cases, conventional seeds treated with chemicals were mixed with harvested grain (De Oliveira, 2018). Shipments containing unauthorized seeds were rejected by China, triggering a temporary embargo that significantly affected Chinese firms.

Following a sharp increase in soybean demand, Chinese traders turned to the Chicago Board of Trade to purchase soybean futures in order to hedge against potential price increases. However, speculative activity drove contract prices to unusually high levels. By the time these contracts matured, global soybean prices had fallen by nearly 30%, prompting many Chinese buyers to default. The ABCD firms filed claims before the Grain and Feed Trade Association (GAFTA), which ruled in their favor. As a result, Chinese importers were required to pay at least USD 1.5 billion above prevailing market prices (De Oliveira, 2018). The ABCD firms emerged as the principal beneficiaries, subsequently

controlling more than 85% of China's soybean processing capacity (Wen, 2008).

In the aftermath of this crisis, China adopted measures to reduce vulnerabilities in its agricultural supply chain. Wilkinson, Wesz Junior, and Lopane (2016) identify a clear strategy to expand the global presence of Chinese firms and secure access to resources considered strategically essential. Building on the soybean case, María Giraudó (2020) outlines four mechanisms used by China to strengthen food security in Latin America: acquisition of local companies; investment in infrastructure and financial support; influence over biotechnology development; and, to a lesser extent, land purchases—although the latter has remained limited due to restrictive legislation in countries such as Argentina and Brazil.

4.2 Investments as a Strategy for Supply Chain Control

In response to perceived supply risks in the region, Chinese investors have pursued acquisitions of strategic assets. For example, through the purchase of Noble Agri and Nidera, China's COFCO secured control over grain terminals, port facilities, and processing plants in Argentina, Uruguay, Paraguay, and Brazil (Gooch & Gale, 2018).

In Chile, Chinese investment in the agro-industrial sector has expanded steadily over the past 15 years. This trend began in 2010, when COFCO, China's largest state-owned food company, fully acquired the Bisquertt winery, marking the start of a long-term presence in Chile's wine industry. In 2013, Joyvio—part of the same holding group that owns Lenovo—acquired a majority stake in Subsole's fruit production farms, strengthening its position in fruit production and reflecting a broader diversification strategy in key agricultural sectors. In 2019, Joyvio further expanded its presence by fully

acquiring the salmon farming company Australis Seafood (Rehner, Lorie, and Muñoz, 2023).

Additional acquisitions followed. In 2017, Changyu Pioneer Wine fully acquired three Chilean wineries Indómita, Santa Alicia, and Dos Andes, consolidating its position in the wine sector and underscoring growing Chinese interest in Chile's wine assets. In 2018, Jiangsu Yanghe Brewery invested in the San Pedro Tarapacá winery, opting for a minority stake.

In the cherry sector, Gold Anda Agricultural has been a prominent investor. The company entered Chile in 2013, initially focusing on blueberry purchases under the brand Gold Anda Chile. It later expanded its portfolio to include cherries and plums. In 2018, Gold Anda invested USD 10 million to establish its first fruit processing plant in Curicó, marking a significant step in its expansion into Latin America. According to CEO San Xie, this investment represented a key milestone in the company's international growth (Radio Agricultura, 2018).³ Today, Gold Anda distributes fruit through supermarkets, specialty stores, television, and e-commerce platforms in major Chinese cities, and maintains operations in countries such as Australia, South Africa, and Thailand.

Other Chinese investors in the cherry sector operate with a lower profile and are more difficult to categorize, as they often export through Chilean partners and their investment volumes are relatively modest. Nonetheless, several partnerships between Chinese firms and Chilean exporters can be identified, including collaborations between Yogo and Anakena; Pengsheng and QFG; Riverking and Nature South; Mr. Seven Xu and Exportadora Seven; Wonong and HillVilla; Woo

Lee and Aurora Australis/Chill Fresh; Aisen (UK) and Aisen; Junjie and Kingfisher; (Bendición) and Full C; Yuhua and Duofrut; Harvest Time (Hong Kong) and 8 Fuegos; Howard Yeh (Taiwan) and Frutisima; Miss Lian and Expa; and Xianfeng and Almahue.

China's investment approach in Chile's agro-industrial sector differs from that of North American investors, who have also shown strong interest in the Chilean berry market. Interviewees indicate that Chinese firms have tended to focus on acquiring and developing processing facilities, whereas U.S. and Canadian investors have concentrated more on farmland and export-oriented companies. For example, Frutura, a subsidiary of RRG Capital Management, acquired Giddings Fruit in 2023 and Subsole in 2022, both prominent Chilean berry producers. These acquisitions reflect a strategy aimed at direct control over production and the agricultural supply chain. Similarly, Manulife/Hancock Natural Resource Group acquired David Del Curto, a major Chilean company in the sector, and the Canadian pension fund PSP Investments acquired Hortifrut, a leading fruit producer.⁴

³ Founded in 1989 in Shenzhen, China, the company initially focused on fruit logistics and domestic commercialization. Over time, it expanded its operations, beginning to export fruit from China in 2008 and to import products from other parts of the world in 2010.

⁴ In Chile, several companies backed by closed or open investment funds, none of them Chinese, are active in the cherry market. These include Dole, known for its agricultural products, and Del Monte, recognized for its canned fruit and vegetable products. Oppenheimer, a global investment firm, is also among them. Companies such as Subsole, DDC, and Giddings stand out in the fruit sector, while Hortifrut and Chisa focus on fruit production and exports. Unifrutti, Greenvic (which operates farmland), El Parque, and Agricom are also significant players in Chile's agricultural export industry.

5. A Highly Concentrated Market: What Can We Expect from China?

In 2023, nearly 40% of Chile's total exports were destined for China, representing one of the highest levels of trade dependence on China globally and the highest in Latin America.

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In the case of cherries, more than 90% of Chilean exports are shipped to China. Interviewees consistently noted that such reliance on a single market is not ideal and expressed concern about the potential impact of unforeseen disruptions. Given the perishable nature of cherries, any political or economic disturbance affecting the Chinese market could significantly disrupt export flows. The sector is exposed to various external risks, a vulnerability heightened by the fact that cherries are considered a complementary and seasonal product in China. A recent example was the sharp decline in Chilean cherry sales in January and February 2020, when the rapid spread of COVID-19 in China reduced demand at the end of the export season.

Despite this high degree of trade concentration, Chinese capital does not appear to play a major direct role in Chile's domestic cherry production. Although exports are heavily dependent on the Chinese market, the relationship remains primarily commercial in nature. There is no evidence to suggest that cherry exports are being used as part of a broader Chinese political or strategic agenda. Similarly, it would be inaccurate to argue that the cherry boom alone could generate a Dutch disease effect, given that Chile's

economy continues to rely predominantly on mining. However, the expansion of fruit exports has affected the competitiveness of certain other crops. While Chinese investment in farmland remains limited, its presence in export-related activities is growing, and further expansion of Chinese-capital firms operating in Chile remains possible.

The increase in cherry production has been accompanied by the introduction of new varieties and the expansion of cultivation across different climatic zones. In some areas, cherry orchards have replaced traditional crops such as grapes and apples. Nevertheless, uncertainties persist regarding the long-term sustainability of this growth and its implications for infrastructure and resource management.

When asked about the concentration of exports in China, interviewees emphasized economic considerations. China offers higher prices and lower entry barriers compared to other Asian markets, such as South Korea. Producers also noted that China imposes fewer regulatory requirements than markets such as the United States or the European Union. While these markets do import Chilean cherries, they do so at lower price levels.

For these reasons, there is broad recognition of the need to diversify export destinations to reduce dependence on a single market. Current efforts focus on expanding exports into Southeast Asia, including Indonesia, Vietnam, Singapore, Taiwan, and Thailand, with the aim of broadening market access and strengthening export diversification.

6. Constraints on the Agro-Industrial Development of the Cherry Sector

The global cherry industry is undergoing significant change as new suppliers enter the market. Traditionally, Chile, New Zealand, and Australia have dominated global supply. More recently, Argentina and South Africa have expanded their participation, and pilot initiatives are underway in Peru. In the Northern Hemisphere, countries such as Canada, the United States, Turkey, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, and the United Kingdom are either expanding production or exploring opportunities in the sector. This broader geographic diversification is intensifying competition and placing pressure on Chile's leadership in the sector. In response to this evolving landscape, diversification has become a central strategic consideration. Countries such as New Zealand and Australia have demonstrated the value of diversifying both markets and products, including expansion into wine and other agricultural exports, particularly in Southeast Asia.

In Chile, there remains a widespread perception that the cherry export market still offers significant room for growth. The 2019–2020 IQconsulting yearbook projected continued expansion based on three factors: the potential to reach inland Chinese cities, room for downward price adjustments to expand consumption, and the ability to sustain consumer demand through retail promotion strategies.

Interviewees report that industry discussions frequently emphasize the scale of Chinese demand, suggesting that even if the country were entirely planted with

cherry orchards, production would still fall short of satisfying the market. This perception reinforces the view that Chile has not yet reached its production ceiling and that conditions remain favorable for continued expansion.

The outlook for Chile's cherry industry has shifted notably in recent years, with significant investment in new cherry orchards, particularly in southern regions such as Osorno. This southward expansion represents a major change in the traditional geography of cherry production in Chile, which has historically been concentrated in the central region.

In recent years, the geographic distribution of cherry production has shifted notably. Significant investment has been directed toward new orchards in southern regions such as Osorno, marking a departure from the traditional concentration of production in central Chile. Many of these southern orchards have not yet reached full productive capacity, indicating that national supply is expected to increase substantially as they mature.

However, this southward expansion presents logistical and economic challenges. Production costs in southern regions tend to exceed those in central Chile due to several factors:

1. **Labor:** Lower population density may result in higher labor costs and limited availability.
2. **Energy and Water:** Utility costs, including electricity and water, can be higher, directly affecting production expenses.
3. **Transport:** The limited number of processing plants in the south requires long-distance transport

to central facilities for packing and processing, increasing logistics costs.

4. Climatic Conditions: Southern climates may pose additional risks, requiring greater investment in crop protection and orchard management.

These factors make production in southern Chile more complex and capital-intensive. However, expansion into these regions also offers potential advantages, including geographic diversification and the possibility of extending the harvest window, which may strengthen Chile's position in global markets.

Three key areas have been identified to strengthen infrastructure in the cherry sector. First, there is a need to build additional processing plants, particularly in the southern regions. Second, improvements in road infrastructure and refrigerated logistics are necessary to facilitate efficient delivery to ports while preserving fruit quality. Third, modernization of water management systems, including canal infrastructure upgrades, is essential to address climate variability and ensure long-term sustainability.

Addressing these constraints will require coordinated investment in infrastructure, more efficient logistics strategies, and innovation in cultivation and resource management practices. These measures will be critical to maintaining the viability and profitability of Chile's expanding cherry sector.

7. Future Challenges

This section examines two structural constraints affecting Chile's agro-industrial development in the cherry sector: water scarcity and labor shortages. It then outlines the principal policy approaches aimed at addressing these challenges, considering Chile's integration into international markets and its broader development model.

7.1. Water Scarcity

Demand for cherries must be understood within the broader framework of agricultural production in Latin America, which is increasingly shaped by international demand for high-value products. Rising global consumption of certain agricultural goods can significantly influence production regions through market dynamics, even when producers and consumers are not directly connected.

Serrano and Brooks (2019), for example, analyze the expansion of avocado production in Colombia and conclude that global food systems can reshape agricultural regions irrespective of direct producer-consumer linkages. Similarly, Madariaga Maillet and Rozas (2021) find that the avocado boom in Chile has intensified water scarcity in producing areas.

Water scarcity currently occupies a central place in Chile's public debate. Longstanding disputes over water distribution have been exacerbated by recurring drought conditions. The current institutional framework dates back to the 1981 Water Code, enacted during the military dictatorship. The reform was grounded in market principles and sought to promote efficiency in water allocation by assigning economic value to water. It defined water as an economic good and facilitated privatization through the granting of free and perpetual water use rights, creating what has been described as a "water rights market" (Larraín, 2006). The reform replaced a centralized administrative system with a privatized regime and established two types of water

rights: consumptive rights, in which water is not returned to its source, and non-consumptive rights, in which water can be returned.

Agriculture is the largest consumer of water in Chile and holds the majority of water use rights. Approximately 70% of the country's available freshwater is allocated to irrigation (MOP, 2013, cited in Santibáñez, 2016). As a result, water use in agriculture becomes a critical issue under drought conditions, given the sector's importance to national development and its high level of resource consumption.

Chile is currently experiencing recurring droughts that have placed water scarcity at the forefront of the political agenda. These conditions directly constrain the short- and medium-term development of the agro-industrial sector. Interviewees echoed this concern, pointing to a sustained decline in traditional water sources.

In response, farmers in the most affected areas have adopted mitigation strategies. One common measure has been the drilling of deep wells to extract groundwater from aquifers, thereby reducing competition for surface water. However, deep wells offer only a short-term solution. Aquifers have limited recharge capacity, which depends directly on surface infiltration processes. Interviewees emphasized that groundwater extraction alone cannot address the structural nature of the problem.

Greater attention has also been given to irrigation efficiency. Producers reported transitioning to drip irrigation systems, which can achieve efficiency rates of around 90%, compared with approximately 80% for sprinkler systems. This shift has contributed to improved water conservation.

Producers consistently identify water availability as the principal constraint on the future expansion of Chilean agriculture. The effects of scarcity are already visible in several production regions and could intensify if cherry cultivation were to evolve into a dominant monoculture. Strengthening water management is

therefore essential to safeguarding the long-term sustainability of the agro-industrial sector. This requires a detailed assessment of the current water distribution system at both local and national levels, identification of structural weaknesses, and the development of policy measures capable of addressing these constraints.

7.2. Labor shortages

This case study suggests that labor shortages may constitute a structural constraint on Chile's agro-industrial development. Although the issue is long term in nature, its effects are already visible. Interviewees report increasing difficulty in securing workers during the cherry harvest season, which requires a large labor force concentrated within a short timeframe due to the need for rapid and careful picking.

The expansion of cherry cultivation has intensified demand for labor at specific times and in particular regions. This has led to the recruitment of workers from urban areas, other regions of the country, and abroad. As production continues to grow, competition for workers is expected to increase, further complicating the recruitment of sufficient labor during peak harvest periods.

The growth of the cherry sector is reshaping Chile's agricultural labor market, particularly for temporary workers. Cherry harvesting has become especially attractive because it offers significantly higher wages than traditional crops such as blueberries, grapes, and stone fruits. However, the harvest seasons of these crops overlap, creating labor shortages in other sectors as workers shift toward cherry production.

Higher wages in cherry harvesting have therefore altered labor allocation within agriculture. As seasonal workers gravitate toward more profitable opportunities, producers of blueberries, grapes, and stone fruits face mounting pressure to remain competitive. To attract and retain labor, these sectors may need to raise wages, improve working conditions, or introduce

additional incentives. At the same time, this dynamic may accelerate efforts to mechanize certain processes or adopt technological innovations aimed at reducing reliance on seasonal labor.

Chile's fruit industry has been an exception within agriculture, as labor demand has remained high despite advances in mechanization. In fruit crops where quality standards are strict, mechanized harvesting is often not feasible. As a result, fruit production has contributed to rising demand for agricultural labor. This trend reflects two factors: the shift toward more labor-intensive fruit varieties on land previously dedicated to other crops, and the expansion of fruit cultivation into new areas. Between 2002 and 2017, labor-intensive crops such as blueberries and cherries expanded significantly.

Concerns regarding labor shortages are also linked to rising labor costs. Direct costs relate to higher wage expectations, while indirect costs stem from the difficulty of recruiting and retaining workers. This has strengthened workers' bargaining power, particularly in relation to harvest timing, affecting sector profitability. Demographic trends—including population aging and higher levels of education—are expected to reduce the available labor pool, while seasonal labor demand may continue to grow in the absence of policy interventions. Improving productivity will therefore be critical to mitigating these pressures.

Coordination challenges have also been identified in the agricultural labor market, particularly during peak demand periods. There is potential for institutional action through the development of public goods aimed at improving workforce coordination. Such a framework could reduce information asymmetries and strengthen coordination among workers, intermediaries, and employers, with the State acting as facilitator and regulator.

Specific policy proposals include the creation of a municipal-level labor supply and demand monitoring system for the fruit sector, supported by digital platforms to increase transparency. For foreign labor, the introduction of structured temporary worker

programs, similar to those in Australia, New Zealand, and the United States, has been proposed. These systems would define entry conditions, required qualifications, and seasonal labor quotas.

More broadly, a study by Chile's Office of Agricultural Studies and Policies (ODEPA) has identified five public policy priorities for strengthening the agricultural labor market by 2030: enhancing coordination through research and development; improving training and human resource management in technical education; generating public goods to reduce labor market asymmetries; strengthening childcare support and incentives for women workers; and improving dissemination and understanding of labor regulations among employers and workers.

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These labor challenges must be situated within Chile's broader strategy of positioning itself as an agri-food power, a process in which the fruit industry plays a central role. The cherry industry illustrates ongoing technological advancements, including harvest alignment with the Lunar New Year, the use of machine learning in packaging, and controlled temperature systems. The literature emphasizes the importance of scale economies and the State's role in providing sector-specific public goods, such as national branding, Free Trade Agreements, and institutional support to sustain competitiveness (Agosin and Bravo-Ortega, 2009). In this context, fruit exports are part of a broader effort to diversify Chile's export structure.

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